

Information Culture Survey

Introduction

Firstly, thanks for taking time to complete this questionnaire. This survey has been designed to help understand how 'XXXX' employees interact with and use data as part of their day-to-day jobs. The results will be used to define the information strategy at 'XXXX' moving forward.

All responses are anonymous, and will be managed by 'YYYY' who are obliged to protect collected data under the EU General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) 2018.

Please answer the questions as honestly as possible as this is essential for the survey to be helpful and accurate in describing the existing information culture of the business.

Thank you for participating - your feedback is incredibly important.

Information Culture Survey

Section 1: Values and Norms

1. Are you aware of 'XXX' Vision and Strategy?

- Yes
 No

2. How much does your knowledge of 'XXX' Vision and Strategy influence your information use approach?

Not at All Very Little Neutral Somewhat To a Great Extent

3. How much does your knowledge of 'XXX' good performance motivate your work?

Not at All Very Little Neutral Somewhat To a Great Extent

4. Do you understand the differences between policies, standards, procedures and guidelines?

Not at All Very Little Neutral Somewhat To a great Extent

5. Do you pay attention to the appropriate use of policies, standards, procedures and guidelines in your information use?

Not at All Very Little Neutral Somewhat To a great Extent

6. My team has a unique way of managing information compared to other teams

Strongly Disagree Disagree Undecided Agree Strongly Agree

Information Culture Survey

Section 2: Practices

7. How often do you use any of the following technologies for 'XXXX' work?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Always
GPS Devices	<input type="radio"/>				
RFID Tags	<input type="radio"/>				
Wireless Sensors	<input type="radio"/>				
Barcode Reader	<input type="radio"/>				
Digital Camera	<input type="radio"/>				
3D Laser Camera	<input type="radio"/>				
Voice Recorder	<input type="radio"/>				
Video Recorder	<input type="radio"/>				
Radar (Ultra Wide Band) Devices	<input type="radio"/>				
Mobile Apps	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

8. To what extent do you rely on the following sources of information for your day-to-day work?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Always
Email	<input type="radio"/>				
Magazines	<input type="radio"/>				
Social Media	<input type="radio"/>				
Scholarly Journals	<input type="radio"/>				
Personal Notes	<input type="radio"/>				
Team Repository	<input type="radio"/>				
Organisation Repository	<input type="radio"/>				
Industry Partners	<input type="radio"/>				
Regulatory Bodies	<input type="radio"/>				
Research Groups	<input type="radio"/>				
Decision Support Systems	<input type="radio"/>				

Other (please specify)

9. The way I currently seek information for use on tasks or projects is streamlined (i.e. effective and efficient)

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

10. How often do you correct the data you receive before use?

Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Always
<input type="radio"/>				

11. How often do you combine data from multiple sources for a task?

Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Always
<input type="radio"/>				

12. Among the people I work with regularly, it is common to distribute information used for decisions made

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

13. Among the people I work with regularly, it is normal to use 'XXX' data for unofficial purposes

Strongly Disagree

Disagree

Undecided

Agree

Strongly Agree

14. I use informal information sources (e.g. colleagues) to check validity and improve the quality of formal information sources (e.g. memos, reports)

Strongly Disagree

Disagree

Undecided

Agree

Strongly Agree

15. I receive information about the performance of my organisation

Never

Rarely

Sometimes

Very Often

Always

16. In my organisation, data collection is essential to organisational performance measurement

Strongly Disagree

Disagree

Undecided

Agree

Strongly Agree

17. Information sharing

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Communication channels are very open here among employees	<input type="radio"/>				
Information is distributed on a 'need to know' basis	<input type="radio"/>				
Information is organised to make it easy to find what I need	<input type="radio"/>				
I often exchange information with entities outside my organisation	<input type="radio"/>				
Communication channels are very open here among management and workers	<input type="radio"/>				
Information about good work practices, lessons learned, and knowledgeable persons is easy to find in my organisation	<input type="radio"/>				
Seniors training subordinates is encouraged	<input type="radio"/>				

18. Proactive use of information

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
Management actively solicit input from employees before major decisions are made	<input type="radio"/>				
The people I work with regularly communicate information on failures or errors to address problems constructively	<input type="radio"/>				
I use information to create or enhance my organisation's products, services, and processes	<input type="radio"/>				

19. Archiving of information

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Always
I store data for new project on my desktop	<input type="radio"/>				
I store data for new project on a removable drive	<input type="radio"/>				
I follow the recommendations in a formal document on back up frequency	<input type="radio"/>				
I follow the recommendations in a formal document when deleting work information	<input type="radio"/>				

20. I have deletion rights on the shared information systems I use

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
<input type="radio"/>				

Information Culture Survey

Section 3: General Management

21. Information Technology Resources

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Undecided	Agree	Strongly Agree
My organisation has a central IT infrastructure to facilitate knowledge and information storage and sharing (office+site)	<input type="radio"/>				
My organisation periodically trains employees on information security issues	<input type="radio"/>				
My organisation has formal procedures to share knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				
My organisation has formal procedures to gather knowledge	<input type="radio"/>				

Information Culture Survey

Section 4: About you

22. What part of 'XXXX' do you work?

Other (please specify)

23. What department are you in?

24. How long have you worked for/with 'XXXX'?

- | | |
|-----------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| <input type="radio"/> < 6 Months | <input type="radio"/> 7 -12 Months |
| <input type="radio"/> 1 -2 Years | <input type="radio"/> 3-10 Years |
| <input type="radio"/> 11-20 Years | <input type="radio"/> > 21 Years |

25. Where do you spend the majority of your working

- day? On project sites
- 'XXXX' Offices
- Client Offices

26. What description is closest to your job title?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="radio"/> Operative | <input type="radio"/> Manager - Group Services |
| <input type="radio"/> Supervisor/Team Leader | <input type="radio"/> Group services - Admin/PA |
| <input type="radio"/> Manager -Site/Project | <input type="radio"/> Technical e.g. engineer, designer |
| <input type="radio"/> Manager Business Unit | <input type="radio"/> Executive |

Other (please specify)

27. Please comment on what you think the challenges are with the data you use for your work

Information Culture Survey

End

Thank you!